

TABLE 3—IMPORTANT MASS SPECTRAL FRAGMENTS OF COMPOUNDS

	<i>m/e</i> (% Abundance)				
	2	9	6	13	4
M^{+}	352 (23.60)	382 (18.80)	368 (26.80)	358 (21.70)	410 (69.5)
$M^{+} - H_2O$	334 (0.51)	364 (0.94)	350 (1.23)	340 (0.40)	392 (2.44)
B_1	192 (100)	192 (72.64)	208 (100)	208 (100)	208 (100)
B_2	191 (89.50)	191 (*)	207 (40.5)	207 (42.50)	207 (63.41)
B_3	165 (16.50)	165 (13.90)	181 (7.84)	181 (6.70)	181 (5.0)
B_1-30	162 (3.16)	162 (5.16)	—	—	—
B_1-15	—	—	193 (10.20)	193 (10.0)	193 (15.20)
A_1	160 (5.55)	190 (11.43)	160 (7.8)	154 (10.0)	202 (3.2)
A_2	161 (16.67)	191 (*)	161 (9.8)	161 (5.40)	203 (9.80)

Mass spectrum *trans*-(±)-12_a-hydroxyrotenone: 410 (23.7%, M^{+}), 392 (3.12), 208 (100), 207 (39.6), 203 (15.62), 202 (2.10), 197 (13.54), 191 (12.9), 190 (4.2), 189 (8.3), 183 (18.8), 169 (17.70), 155 (15.6).

* A part of base peak.

it the most abundant base peak. For 9 fragment B_1 is still prominent (72.6%).

The parent ion M^{+} is extraordinarily abundant for 12_a-hydroxyrotenone (69.5%) signifying its chemical and mass spectral stability than other 12_a-hydroxyrotenoids⁹. The low abundance of $M - H_2O^{+}$ dehydrated parent ions conforms to thermodynamic stability of B/C *cis* ring fusion. The fragment B_1 loses formaldehyde (-30 amu) or CH_2 radical (-15 amu) for methylenedioxy and dimethyl compounds, respectively as usual. An important ion B_3 (B_1-27 amu) is uniformly observed for all the compounds and seems to be diagnostic of 12_a-hydroxy compounds. Such odd-electron species as B_3 are considered diagnostically more important than equally abundant even-electron fragments⁹.

Ketene fragments A_1 (R.D.A) and A_2 (R.D.A. with H-transfer) are observed in close similarity to rotenoids.

12_a-Hydroxyrotenone (*trans*-synthetic) fragmented through R.D.A. *etc.* in close similarity to other *cis*-compounds but for two unique fragments at *m/e* 190(4.2%) and 189(8.3%) which were practically absent for *cis*-(-)-12_a-hydroxyrotenone (4). These are presumably dehydration products of B_1 (*m/e*, 208) and B_2 (*m/e*, 207). Also dehydrated parent ion $M - H_2O^{+}$ was much more abundant ($M - H_2O^{+}$

= 1 : 8) as compared with 4 having the same ratio at 1 : 29. Once again comparative thermodynamic stability of *cis*-structure is vindicated.

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Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Trace Amounts of Rhodium with Diphenylcarbazide in Presence of α -Picoline

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Manuscript received 22 May 1984, revised 15 February 1985, accepted 31 July 1985

DIPHENYLCARBAZIDE has long been known as a reagent for the detection and determination of a number of metals¹. It is used as a sensitive and specific reagent for spectrophotometric determination of chromium². With a slightly acidic rhodium(III) solution, it forms a purple coloured complex on heating for a few minutes. In the present investigation, it is found that in presence of α -picoline, rhodium(III) forms with diphenylcarbazide a bluish-violet complex, extractable into methyl isobutyl ketone. Diphenylcarbazide and α -picoline make a suitable ligand pair for the determination of rhodium spectrophotometrically. This forms the basis of the method which has proved to be very sensitive and selective.

Experimental

Absorbance measurement were made with a Hilger-Uvispek spectrophotometer in matched quartz cells of 1 cm optical path.

A stock solution of rhodium(III) was prepared by dissolving rhodium trichloride (Johnson Matthey) in 1 N hydrochloric acid and standardised by known

method⁸. Solutions of lower concentration were prepared by appropriate dilution of the stock solution. A 1% solution of diphenylcarbazide (B.D.H.) in absolute ethanol and a 0.5% solution of α -picoline in distilled water were employed as the reagents. Standard solutions of diverse ions were prepared from analytical grade salts.

Procedure: To an aliquot of the standard aqueous solution containing 1-30 μg of rhodium, 0.5% α -picoline (1 ml) was added and the mixture was made upto 10 ml with water ($\text{pH } 7.4 \pm 0.1$). To this, 1% diphenylcarbazide solution (1 ml) was added and the mixture was heated for 15 min in a boiling water-bath. After cooling, the solution was extracted in a separatory funnel for 5 min with MIBK (10 ml). The organic phase was separated and absorbance of the complex was measured at 560 nm against pure solvent. The rhodium contents were computed from the standard calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

The bluish violet rhodium complex with diphenylcarbazide in presence of α -picoline extractable into MIBK, absorbs at λ_{max} 560 nm and obeys Beer's law over the concentration range of 1-30 μg of rhodium per 10 ml of organic phase. The reagent blank shows no absorbance at 560 nm. Hence, the absorbance of the complex is measured against pure solvent. The Sandell's sensitivity of the colour reaction is $0.0026 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ and molar absorptivity is $4.01 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

The effect of varying reagents concentration on extraction of rhodium was studied. 1 ml of 1% diphenylcarbazide solution and 1 ml of 0.5% α -picoline are adequate for complete extraction of the complex for the range of the concentration of rhodium (1-30 μg) determined. A 0.1-1% solution of α -picoline can be used without any effect on the values of absorbance. Increased diphenylcarbazide concentration also produces no significant effect. For complete colour development, 15 min heating of the metal-ligands mixture in a boiling water-bath is necessary. The colour of the complex is stable for more than 2 h, and 5 min shaking period is adequate for complete extraction. Benzene, toluene, amyl alcohol, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, 1,2-dichloroethane and MIBK were tested as solvent for the extraction but MIBK was found to be the most effective solvent.

Effect of diverse ions: The effect of diverse ions was studied by adding different amounts of foreign ions to 10 μg of rhodium(III) and determining rhodium following the extraction procedure. It was found that Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} , Hg^{II} , V^V , Mo^{VI} , W^{VI} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Pt^{IV} , fluoride, bromide, iodide, cyanide, sulphate, nitrate, nitrite, tartrate, acetate, citrate and EDTA did not interfere even when present in five-fold excess of rhodium and a good recovery of rhodium (within 3% error in microgram level) was achieved. However, equal amounts of Pd^{II} ,

Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Cu^{II} , Cr^{III} , Cr^{VI} , Ir^{III} , Ag^I , Au^{III} , oxalate, and thiocyanate, and five-fold excess of Ru^{III} and Os^{IV} interfere. Equal amounts of Ru^{III} and Os^{IV} do not interfere. Interference due to Cu^{II} can be removed by using EDTA and that due to Pd^{II} by using KI as masking agents. In presence of twenty-fold excess of KBr, both Ag^I and Au^{III} do not interfere.

The standard deviation and coefficient of variation of the absorbance was found to be 0.0042 and 0.54%, respectively for 20 μg of rhodium.

A comparison of the present method with some of the earlier methods shows that the present method is more sensitive⁴ and simple.

Acknowledgement

The authors sincerely thank Prof. (Mrs.) A. Chaudhuri for facilities.

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Spectrophotometric Determination of Traces of Sulphite in Sugar Samples

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Manuscript received 4 April 1985, revised 8 April 1985,
accepted 3 August 1985

A number of spectrophotometric methods for the determination of sulphite have been reported in the literature which involve the use of either rosaniline or pararosaniline hydrochloride dyes¹⁻⁷. The use of crystal violet (N,N,N' -hexamethylpararosaniline) dye for the determination of sulphite has been reported here. The method has been studied in details in comparison to earlier works^{8,9}. The proposed method has been applied for the determination of sulphur dioxide in white sugar samples. The composition of the sulphite-crystal violet compound has also been determined.

Experimental

Crystal violet (Sigma) was used to prepare a 0.008 M stock solution in 25% (v/v) ethanol-water. A 0.0048 M stock sulphite solution was prepared by dissolving reagent grade $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_5$ (E. Merck) in double-distilled water. A 0.25 M formaldehyde